
Technological Preparedness of Elementary Teachers at Subic Central School: Implications to Instructional Development

Judith Pasustento

Ediric D. Gadia*

Narcissa R. Figuerres

Institute of Graduate Studies

Gordon College

**Corresponding Author*

ABSTRACT

Integrating Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) into the educational system is crucial for enhancing teaching practices and student learning outcomes. This study explores the technological preparedness of elementary teachers at Subic Central School in Subic, Zambales, focusing on the implications for instructional development. The study examines how the Department of Education's initiatives, such as the ICT Framework and the National Strategic Planning Initiative for ICTs in Basic Education, have impacted the readiness of teachers to incorporate ICT into their pedagogy. Employing a descriptive research design, data were gathered through questionnaires, observations, and interviews with 52 regular permanent teachers from Subic Central School. The findings reveal that while teachers demonstrate a moderate level of technological preparedness, there are significant gaps in access to ICT facilities and the effective integration of ICT in teaching practices. The study underscores the need for continuous professional development and infrastructure support to harness the potential of ICT in education fully. The results suggest that addressing these challenges through targeted programs significantly improves the region's instructional development and overall educational outcomes.

Keywords: ICT, Technological preparedness, Elementary teachers, Instructional development

How to Cite (APA): Pasustento, J., Gadia, E.D., & Figuerres, N.R. (2023). Technological preparedness of elementary teachers at Subic central school: Implications to instructional development. *Journal of Scholarly Graduate Researches*, 1(1), 52-58. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14835832>

INTRODUCTION

Organizations of all types and sizes, including schools, have recognized that the use of computers in the work environment is important. It presents unique challenges that help individuals acquire an inquiring, critical, and creative mind to make the most of the opportunities driven by the explosive growth of information, knowledge, and technology.

The goal of the new curriculum, the "Department of Education Information Technology Framework," lays down the action areas for ICT integration in the basic education system. These include school computerization, teacher training, IT curriculum development, multimedia content development, financing, and monitoring and evaluation. Bayucca (2020) stated that teachers in DepEd displayed proficiency in basic ICT skills. Obispo et al. (2022) also mentioned that computer-assisted instruction aids in better teacher-student communication and learning outcomes. Natividad and Natividad (2021) also noted that several factors, such as the application of technology and technology literacy, correlated with the teacher's

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preparedness. Mariani et al. (2023) also stated that technological preparedness positively impacts student learning outcomes.

Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), the diverse set of technological tools and resources used to communicate and to create, disseminate, store, and manage information, such as computers, the Internet, radio, television, telephones, and audiovisual equipment, can support the qualitative shift in the learning process, facilitate access to education, and improve administrative and instructional efficiency. Asio and Riego de Dios (2019; 2018) recognized the importance of information, media, and technology skills among educators. Recognizing the potential benefits of integrating ICTs in education systems, DepEd launched the National Strategic Planning Initiative for ICTs in Basic Education as part of a system-wide reform process to bring Philippine basic education out of crisis. The importance of ICT in education has prompted the researcher to design a project named 'Preparing the Next Generation of Teachers through ICT.' This project aims to assist teacher education institutions prepare teachers on how and when to best use the technologies for teaching and learning. It is one of the most recent initiatives for the professional development of teachers.

One of the challenges facing the Education Department is ensuring that the teachers have the necessary skills to combine pedagogy and knowledge of today's technologies in the classroom and continue to develop and adapt to new technologies that will emerge in the future. De Vera et al. (2020) explained that teachers experience different struggles in preparation for instructional methodologies. Another issue was the inadequate ICT devices, contributing to teachers' inadequacy. (Omboto, 2022). In introducing the K to 12 Program, teachers must adopt the Guidelines on the Assessment and Rating of Learning Outcomes as stipulated in the DepEd Order No. 73, s. 2012. The attainment of learning outcomes as defined in the standards shall be the basis for the quality assurance of learning using formative assessments. They shall also be the focus of the summative assessments and the basis for grading at the end of instruction. Hence, teachers must be technologically equipped. Abedi et al. (2022) claimed that the teacher's preparedness to teach with technology was less favorable since technology resources, limited practicum experience, and inadequate technological methodology training.

Moreover, the National Competency-Based Teachers Standard (NCBTS), stipulated in the DepEd Order No. 32, s. 2010. ICT competency was included, and that will make teachers embrace the changes ICT will effect on teaching and learning, adopt a positive outlook, and perceive ICT as an opportunity to develop their pedagogy and professionalism in line with global trends in education, shift from being the traditional providers of knowledge to becoming the facilitator of learning and try to become habitual users of ICT. A past study by Asio et al. (2019) endorsed that teachers have excellent remarks regarding professional skills. Vogt (2021) also explored topics focusing on professional development in the technological pedagogy content knowledge (TPACK) and recommended additional research on the said area to understand the effectiveness of technology integration fully. A recent investigation by Zhakiyanova et al. (2023) revealed that teachers' TPACK competencies were at a medium level, and variances were seen in technology knowledge regarding sex.

The existence of ICTs does not transform teacher practices in and of itself. However, ICTs can enable teachers to transform their practices, given enabling conditions. For instance, in the pandemic, a change of teaching mode is necessary. Therefore, implementing the alternative delivery mode of learning is pertinent (Asio & Jimenez, 2021). Teachers' pedagogical practices and reasoning influence their uses of ICT, and the nature of teacher ICT use impacts pupils' achievement. Using ICTs as presentation tools (through overhead and LCD projectors, television, electronic whiteboards, and guided web tours, where students simultaneously view the same resources on computer screens) is of mixed effectiveness. While it may promote class understanding of and discussion about complex concepts (primarily through the display simulations), such uses of ICTs can reinforce traditional pedagogical practices and divert focus from the

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content of what is being discussed or displayed to the tool being utilized. Margiewicz (2023) also claimed that areas of support for teacher-education programs and school districts could provide better-equipped educators with the implementation of technology in instruction.

Thus, schools and educational systems must provide the infrastructure and support for students and teachers and maintain constructivist learning environments in which ICT is used. At the same time, ICT tools will assist schools and educational systems carry this out.

With this problem, the researcher was motivated to undertake the study to propose a program to strengthen the Technological Preparedness of Elementary Teachers at Subic Central School: Implications to Instructional Development in Subic, Zambales.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used the descriptive type of research. Descriptive research falls under the general category of quantitative design, which involves respondents representing a specific population (Asio, 2021). It is concerned with conditions or relationships, opinions that are held, processes that are going on, evident effects, or trends that are developing. It is primarily concerned with the present, although it often considers past events and influences related to current conditions.

Moreover, descriptive studies describe a given state of affairs as thoroughly and carefully as possible. Most descriptive researchers want to have a more complete understanding of people and things. It requires a more detailed analysis of the various aspects of phenomena and their relationships.

Respondents

The study was conducted in Subic Central Elementary School in the District of Subic, Division of Zambales. The target respondents are the public elementary school teachers and master teachers who are directly involved in the subject of the study.

Fifty-two (52) regular permanent teachers of Subic Central School were the respondents of this study. They handled an advisory class and a SY 2013-2014 departmental schedule. Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents per Grade Level. Subic Central School is the most prominent school in Subic, Zambales, which currently employs the target respondents of fifty-two (52) regular permanent teachers. For Grades I, ten sections employ ten teacher advisers. Grades II and V have nine sections with nine teacher advisers. While Grades III, IV, and VI have eight sections with eight teacher advisers. The majority of these belong to the Grade One level.

Instrumentation

The data needed for this study were obtained mainly through a questionnaire. Observations and informal interviews will likewise be conducted to support or verify the respondents' responses to the questionnaire.

The results gathered from the auxiliary methods substantiated the data obtained from the questionnaire.

The study, designed primarily for teachers, used a questionnaire to evaluate the Technological Preparedness of the Elementary Teachers at Subic Central School: Implications to Instructional Development.

The research instrument consisted of three (3) parts: Part I-This part dealt with the personal profile of the respondents as to age, gender, highest educational attainment/ specialization, length of teaching experience, teaching position, and seminars. Part II -This part pertained to the Technological Preparedness of Teachers, which includes the availability of computer hardware, access to ICT facilities, nature of computer use,

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frequency of computer use in teaching, and integration of ICT in education. Part III – These are perceived significant obstacles affecting the Preparedness of Teachers to use ICT in Instruction.

Further, to determine the instrument's validity and reliability, the questionnaire was given to 12 teachers of Del Pilar Elementary School, Castillejos, Zambales.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data gathered from the questionnaire were collected and presented in tables. The appropriate statistical treatment used in the study includes the following: Percentage and frequency distribution were used to organize and describe the personal profile of the respondents. As to age, gender, highest educational attainment/ specialization, length of teaching experience, teaching position, and seminars, Weighted Mean and Descriptive Rating were used since different groups of respondents contributed to an overall average. The weighted mean measured the technological preparedness of elementary teachers at Subic Central School and its implication to instructional development.

Ethical Consideration

The research process prioritizes the ethical principle of respect for autonomy by ensuring that all respondents are fully informed of their rights by including consent forms attached to the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the research adheres to the Data Privacy Act (Republic Act 10173), which safeguards the privacy and confidentiality of respondents' information. The researcher is responsible for protecting personal data, ensuring that all information provided by the respondents is securely handled and used solely for the purposes outlined in the study, with no unauthorized access or disclosure. It reflects a commitment to maintaining the confidentiality and privacy of the participants, thereby respecting their dignity and rights.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section showcases the results from the gathered data.

Level of Information Technology Competence

The overall mean assessment is 3.49 with a descriptive rating of “Prepared”. The percentage of awareness with the competencies in the technological preparedness of the teacher-respondents is enough to meet the requirements of the learning needs of the modern learners.

Availability of Computer Hardware

The overall mean of 4.10, the respondents “Agreed” that technological availability affects the readiness of the teachers in the use of computer technology.

Access to ICT Facilities

The overall mean assessment of 2.63 with a descriptive rating of “Sometimes”. The percentage of technological preparedness of the respondents in the use of access to ICT technology is not enough to suffice the learning needs of the modern learners.

Nature of use of Computer

Technological preparedness of the respondents in the nature use of the computer measured how the technology is being applied showed that the teacher-respondents have poor skill with the descriptive rating of “Most of the Time” at the weighted mean of 3.44.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are presented: The study concluded that the elementary teachers at Subic Central School are generally prepared in terms of their information technology competence, with a readiness level that meets the learning needs of modern students. However, this technological preparedness is significantly influenced by the availability of computer hardware and access to ICT facilities. While teachers agree that access to technology impacts their readiness, the study revealed that the current access to ICT facilities is insufficient to support their needs fully. Furthermore, the nature of computer uses in teaching indicated that teachers predominantly utilize technology for traditional purposes, with limited application in innovative or constructivist approaches to education. While teachers possess basic technological skills, there is a gap in integrating these tools effectively to enhance instructional practices.

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations were endorsed:

1. **Enhanced ICT Infrastructure:** To address the identified gaps in technological preparedness, it is recommended that Subic Central School and the Division of Zambales prioritize the enhancement of ICT infrastructure. This includes improving access to computer hardware and ensuring that teachers have reliable and consistent access to ICT facilities.
2. **Comprehensive ICT Training:** The study suggests that ongoing professional development programs should be implemented, focusing on the effective integration of ICT in teaching. These programs should move beyond basic skills training to include strategies for incorporating technology into innovative pedagogical practices.
3. **Support for Constructivist Learning Environments:** Schools should provide continuous support and resources for the development and maintenance of constructivist learning environments. This would encourage teachers to move away from traditional instructional methods and towards more student-centered, technology-enhanced learning experiences.
4. **Monitoring and Evaluation:** A system-wide monitoring and evaluation framework should be established to assess the effectiveness of ICT integration in teaching. This framework should include regular feedback from teachers and students to ensure that the implemented strategies are meeting educational goals.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study involved the elementary school teachers of Subic Central School in Subic, Zambales, who are teaching for the School Year 2013-2014. Subic Central School is the most prominent school in Subic, Zambales, which currently employs the target respondents of fifty-two (52) regular permanent teachers. For Grades I, ten sections employ ten teacher advisers. Grades II and V have nine sections with nine teacher advisers. While Grades III, IV, and VI have eight sections with eight teacher advisers. The coverage of the study is on the self-competency assessment of elementary school teachers that could serve as the basis for in-service education and in attaining effective classroom instruction. The content of the questionnaire includes items designed to seek personal information and data on the level of competencies in the different areas. In the Use of Specific Technology at school, the skill of applying these technologies is being measured. And in the Technological Preparedness of Elementary Teachers Implications to Instructional Development.

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